

Deliverable 2.4

Workpackage WP2-T3-ST1

Responsible Partners: ISS and DTU

Contributing partners: IP, VISAVET, WUR,
PIWET, ISS, SVA

GENERAL INFORMATION

European Joint Programme full title	Promoting One Health in Europe through joint actions on foodborne zoonoses, antimicrobial resistance and emerging microbiological hazards
European Joint Programme acronym	One Health EJP
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DOCUMENT MANAGEMENT

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D2.4 Genome assemblies and raw reads deposited at ENA

This deliverable consists of making publicly available the WGS of strains chosen as Reference Materials if the data were reported as lacking at the end of the inventory phase (see D.2.1)

It was decided during the project that only raw reads should be uploaded. QC analyses of the raw reads and genome assemblies if required were made at INRAE. All the involved partners have deposited their data by using these paragraphs to describe the study scope :

Data on occurrence of antibiotic resistance and the use of antibiotics in animals and humans are now perfectly well integrated in a One-Health Action Plan at European level. There is still a lack in providing sets of reference materials for microbiological testing. It is time now set up a repository of resources coupling strains, genomes, and associated data that would represent the great variety of resistance mechanisms reported among food-borne zoonotic pathogens. The network of EJP partners will deliver referenced panels of strains usable for antibiotic resistance prevention, surveillance or control studies, development of innovative diagnostic tests, and laboratory challenges of novel antibiotic compounds.

Or :

This project is part of the One Health European Joint Project CARE (Cross-sectoral framework for quality Assurance Resources for countries in the European Union). The objective of CARE is to enhance collaboration between the public health, food and animal health sectors across the EU, in order to increase joint preparedness, in relation to bacterial zoonotic (especially foodborne) infections. One of the main topics of CARE is to provide a collection of reference materials (RM) of zoonotic pathogens from different sectors to be used e.g., for validation of methods and organisation of proficiency tests.

Or :

The objective of CARE is to enhance collaboration between the public health, food and animal health sectors across the EU, in order to increase joint preparedness, in relation to bacterial zoonotic (especially foodborne) infections as mentioned in the priority topics. The project aims to set standards that will strengthen already existing systems for proficiency testing, reference material and quality/availability of demographic data. This study groups genomic sequences of pathogenic E. coli or Yersinia enterocolitica strains made available by the Istituto Superiore di Sanità, Rome, Italy.

The list and details of the strains can be found at the following accession numbers :

PRJEB46213 : 22 strains of Yersinia (Institut Pasteur, France)

Study Name: OHEJP CARE YERSINIA

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-09-11

PRJEB49020 : 30 strains of Yersinia (VISAVET, Spain)

Study Name: Y.enterocolitica-OHEJP-CARE

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-28

PRJEB49018 : 30 strains of Staphylococcus aureus (VISAVET, Spain)

Study Name: S.aureus-OHEJP-CARE

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-28

PRJEB49008 : 8 strains of Salmonella (VISAVET, Spain)

Study Name: Salmonella-OHEJP-CARE

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-28

PRJEB49009 : 2 strains of Campylobacter (VISAVET, Spain)

Study Name: Campylobacter-OHEJP-CARE

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-28

PRJEB48968 : 34 strains of Escherichia coli (VISAVET, Spain)

Study Name: STEC-OHEJP-CARE

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-28

PRJEB48148 : 23 strains of Campylobacter (WUR, Netherlands)

Study Name: OHEJP CARE Campylobacter

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-10-18

PRJEB48129 : 12 strains of Campylobacter (SVA, Sweden)

Study Name: EJP CARE - SVA

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-11-12

PRJEB47991 : 16 strains of Escherichia coli (ISS, Italy)

Study Name: OHEJP CARE ISS E. coli

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-12-03

PRJEB49418 : 8 strains of Yersinia enterocolitica (ISS, Italy)

Study Name: OHEJP CARE ISS Yersinia enterocolitica

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-01-05

PRJEB49424 : 122 strains of Salmonella (Institut Pasteur, France)

Study Name: Salmonella reference genomes

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2021-12-16

PRJNA799608 : 6 strains of Bacillus cereus group (PIWET, Poland)

Study Name: Bacillus cereus group isolates from reptiles

ENA-FIRST-PUBLIC: 2022-02-03